

The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Environment on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the influence of learning facilities and the learning environment on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. The type of research used by researchers is correlational, with a research population of all class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, totaling 223 students. Data collection techniques use instruments: (1) learning facilities questionnaire, (2) learning environment questionnaire, and (3) learning motivation questionnaire. The research results show that: (1) This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value $>$ t table ($3.388 > 1.976$) and the value is significant ($0.001 < 0.05$). (2) These results can be seen in the partial calculation (t test) of the learning environment (X2) showing the calculated t value $<$ t table ($-2.240 < 1.976$) and a significant value ($0.027 > 0.05$). (3) This can be seen from the results of the simultaneous calculation (F test) of the Learning Facilities (X1) and the learning environment (X2) which was carried out using SPSS 21.0, namely showing the calculated f value $>$ f table ($5.776 > 1.655$) and a significant value ($0.004 < 0.05$).

INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital thing which everyone must obtain in order to adapt to the progress of the times which requires everyone to have knowledge so as not to be left behind.

Learning facilities include all the facilities needed in the teaching and learning process, both moving and immovable so that the achievement of educational goals can run smoothly, regularly, effectively and efficiently so that a person can achieve optimal learning achievement. Learning facilities are closely related to learning motivation, the presence of complete learning facilities can raise student motivation in carrying out learning activities which will ultimately determine student learning success, so it can be said that student learning success is not only determined by complete facilities but also high learning motivation. from the students themselves. The learning environment consists of three, namely the school environment, family environment and community environment."

The scope of the school environment includes, 1) The physical environment of the school: teaching methods, teacher-student relationships, student-student relationships and school discipline.

The definition of learning motivation according to Sardiman (2018: 75) is the overall driving force within students which gives rise to learning activities and provides direction to learning activities, so that the goals desired by the learning subject can be achieved. The various types of motivation consist of motivation that comes from within a person's self which is called intrinsic motivation and motivation that comes from outside a person is called extrinsic motivation.

Extrinsic Motivation Extrinsic motivation is motivation that involves stimulation from outside the individual such as praise, advice, encouragement, rewards, punishment, and imitating something. The learning environment at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar is still in the less comfortable category, this is because the location is less strategic, namely on the side of the road, so that when they come home from school, many students congregate which can endanger student safety.

This can be seen from students who often come late so that their own motivation becomes less, and in doing homework assignments (PR), there are also those who do not do their homework assignments (PR), so that their motivation to learn decreases and can also cause students to lazy in carrying out the learning process in class.

Based on the description above, researchers are interested in research with the title "**The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Environment on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar**".

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Learning Facilities

Popi Sopiadin (2010:73) said that "Learning facilities are the facilities and infrastructure that must be available to facilitate educational activities in

schools. Facilities are all equipment, materials and furniture that are directly used for the education process at school, including buildings, study rooms (classrooms), learning media, tables and chairs. Meanwhile, infrastructure are facilities that indirectly support the course of the educational process, including school yards, school gardens , and roads to schools or tutorials. From this opinion and the two verses above, it can be concluded that learning facilities are anything in the form of movable or immovable objects that can facilitate, expedite and streamline the implementation of learning activities in order to achieve learning goals, so that each school provides appropriate learning facilities and infrastructure. adequate for all educational needs so that students can use it to support student learning.

2. Learning Environment

According to Hamalik (2011: 195) the learning environment is something that exists in the surroundings that has a certain meaning or influence on the individual. Conducive learning environment conditions, both the learning environment, the school environment and the community environment will create calm and comfort for students in learning, so that students will find it easier to master the learning material optimally . In this description, it is known that the student learning environment is everything that appears around students and the factors that influence their development and behavior in carrying out their activities, namely efforts to obtain changes in knowledge (cognitive), attitudes (affective) *and* skills (psychomotor).

3. Motivation to learn

According to Hamzah B. Uno (2013: 9), motivation is an encouragement that arises due to influences from within and outside the individual, so that the individual desires to make changes to certain levels of behavior or activities that are better than the previous situation. Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that learning motivation is an encouragement that arises from within and from outside the individual to provide enthusiasm for learning to make changes so that they can be expected to achieve the goals they want to achieve.

METHODOLOGY

The research used is a quantitative research approach. Meanwhile, the type of research used by researchers is correlational. Quantitative research is a method for testing certain theories by examining the relationships between variables. These variables are measured (usually with research instruments) so that data consisting of numbers can be analyzed based on statistical processes.

Based on the researcher's title "the influence of learning facilities and the learning environment on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar" . This research was carried out at SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar from May to September 2023. The population in this study were all students in class VIII of SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar 7 classes totaling 223 students. The sample in this research was 143 students.

RESEARCH RESULT

Research Instrument Trial Results

Instrument Validity Test

Based on the results of validity calculations using the SPSS 21.0 program, it was found that of the 20 statement items, there were 18 valid statement items and 2 invalid items. As a result of the trial, 35 samples obtained valid and reliable statements, with an r table value of 0.334. The following table shows the results of testing the validity of Learning Facilities (X1)

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.355 while items that have a correlation value (r) < 0.355 are invalid items . This can be concluded that for the questions it is known that there are 60 questions that have a correlation value (r) > 0.355 and as many as 6 questions (r) < 0.355 , it is known that 60 questions have valid data and 6 are invalid. Therefore, the 6 invalid questions were not used for further research.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the question is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is >0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained by learning facilities is 0.797 > 0.60 , Learning Environment is 0.773 > 0.60, and Learning Motivation is 0.867 > 0.60. From the calculation results of learning facilities, learning environment and learning motivation, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Data Normality Test

Table 1. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residuals
N		146
Normal Parameters a, b	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	8,89672009
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,065
	Positive	,065
	Negative	-,049

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	,780
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,577
a. Test distribution is Normal.	
b. Calculated from data.	

Based on the calculation results in table 1, the Kolmogorov Smirnov value for all variables is 0.780 with a significant 0.577 greater than 0.05. This shows that the variable data is normally distributed and on the histogram graph the data is said to be normally distributed because it follows a diagonal line.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 3. Pre-Test Homogeneity Test

In graphic analysis, plots have quite significant weaknesses. Because there is no clear pattern and the distribution of the data is spread above and below or around the number 0, it is concluded that the data does not have symptoms of heteroscedasticity or the assumptions of the heteroscedasticity test have been met. Therefore, statistical tests are needed that can guarantee the accuracy of the results. The statistical test used is the Glejser Test through regression of the *absolute* residual value with the independent variable. The sig value is compared to 0.05. Statistical results can be seen in the table

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Hypothesis Test Results

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	61,117	7,204		8,483	,000	
	Learning Facilities	,421	,124	,391	3,388	,001	,485 2,062
	Learning Environment	-,349	,156	-,259	-2,240	,027	,485 2,062

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation

The multicollinearity test aims to find out whether in the regression model there is a correlation between the independent variables. A good

regression model should have no correlation between independent variables. To determine whether there is multicollinearity or not, it can be seen from the *Variance Inflation Factor* (VIF) and *Tolerance* (a) values. The Independent Variable has a Tolerance Value of more than (0.100) and a VIF of less than (<10.00), so it can be concluded that the Multicollinearity Assumption has been met or there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

Hypothesis testing
Multiple Linear Regression Test

The purpose of the multiple regression analysis test is to determine the direction and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	61,117	7,204		8,483	,000		
	Learning Facilities	,421	,124	,391	3,388	,001	,485	2,062
	Learning Environment	-,349	,156	-,259	-2,240	,027	,485	2,062
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation								

Based on the results of calculations with the SPSS 21 program in the table above, a multiple linear coefficient is obtained for X1=-0.446 X2=-0.397 while the constant is 68.653 so the multiple linear regression equation is:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 61.117 + 0.421X_1 - 0.349X_2 + e$$

The results of the regression equation and interpretation of the multiple regression analysis are that the constant value (a) has a positive sign, namely 61.117, meaning that if the learning facilities and learning environment are equal to zero (0), then learning motivation will increase by 61.117. The regression coefficient value for the learning facilities variable is 0.421. This means that learning facilities (X1) have a positive effect on student learning motivation. The regression coefficient value of the learning environment variable (X2) is -0.349, meaning that the learning environment has a positive effect on student learning motivation. Because 0.421 > -0.349, learning facilities have a more dominant influence on student learning motivation.

Partial Test (T)

The partial test (t) is used to determine whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or $\alpha=5\%$, with the following conditions:

1. If $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t_{\text{count}} < t_{\text{table}}$, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable

Table 6. T Test Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	61,117	7,204		8,483	,000
Learning Facilities	,421	,124	,391	3,388	,001
Learning Environment	-,349	,156	-,259	-2,240	,027

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation

From the table above it can be seen that the t test results for the Learning Facilities variable (X_1) show a calculated t value of 3.388 and a significance value of 0.001. Thus the $\text{calculated } t \text{ value} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($3.388 > 1.976$) and the sig value ($0.001 < 0.05$). This means that H1 is accepted, which means it existsThe influence of learning facilities on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

the results of the t test for the Learning Environment variable (X_2) show a calculated t value of -2.240 and a significance value of 0.027. Thus the $\text{calculated } t \text{ value} < t_{\text{table}}$ ($-2.240 < 1.976$) and the sig value ($0.027 < 0.05$). This means that H2 is rejected, where the learning environment variable (X2) has no influence on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions :

1. If $F_{\text{count}} > F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted
2. If $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$, then H_a is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	927,123	2	463,562	5,776	.004 ^b
	Residual	11476,986	143	80,259		

Total	12404,110	145			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Environment, Learning Facilities					

calculated F value is 5.776 and the sig value is 0.004 Thus $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($5.776 > 1.655$) and the sig value ($0.004 < 0.05$) . This means that H3 is accepted where together there is an influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Environment on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,273 ^a	,075	,062	8.95872
a. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Environment, Learning Facilities				
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation				

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination in this study is an *R square value* of 0.0 75 . The coefficient value of 0.0 75 is equal to 7 , 5 0 % . This value means that the independent variables Learning Facilities and Learning Environment contribute an influence of only 7.5 % to the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile 92,50% is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Learning Facilities on Learning Motivation

Based on the results of data analysis carried out by researchers, several things can be obtained regarding Learning Facilities on Learning Motivation for Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, namely as follows: Based on the multiple linear regression test, the regression equation obtained is $Y=61.117+0.421X_1+-0.349+ e$. This equation illustrates that the influence of learning facilities on student learning motivation is calculated based on the regression coefficient obtained, namely 0.421 . This means that the influence of learning facilities on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar will increase by 0.421. From the results of research and management of t test data, it is known that Learning Facilities (X_1) obtained a calculated t value of 3.388 and a sig value of 0.0 01 at a significance level of 95% or $\alpha=5\%$ and with dk $n-2 = 143$, it was obtained $t_{table} 1.9 76$. So it can be seen that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($3.388 > 1.9 76$) and the sig value ($0.0 01 < 0.05$) . Thus this explains that this means H1 is accepted, which means it existsThe

influence of learning facilities on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

2. The Influence of the Learning Environment on Learning Motivation

Based on the results of data analysis carried out by researchers, several things can be obtained regarding the Influence of the Learning Environment on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, namely as follows: Based on the multiple linear regression test, the regression equation is obtained, namely $Y=61.117+0.421X_1-0.349+e$. This equation illustrates that the Learning Environment on Student Learning Motivation is calculated based on the regression coefficient obtained, namely -0.349 . This means that if the learning environment increases by one unit, the learning motivation of Class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar will increase by -0.349 . From the results of the research and data processing of the t test, it is known that the learning environment variable (X_2) obtained a calculated t value of -2.240 and a significance value of 0.027 . Thus $t_{count} > t_{table} (-2,240 < 1,976)$ and the sig value ($0,027 > 0,05$). This means that H_2 is rejected, where the learning environment variable (X_2) has no influence on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

3. The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Environment on Learning Motivation

Based on the results of data analysis carried out by researchers, several things can be obtained regarding the influence of learning facilities and the learning environment on the learning motivation of Class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar as follows: The results of the multiple linear regression test show the regression equation $Y=61.117+0.421X_1-0.349+e$. This illustrates that if the variables Learning Facilities (X_1) and Learning Environment (X_2) are considered constant then Learning Motivation is 61.117 . If the Learning Facilities variable increases by one unit then MotivationB learn Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar increased by $0,421$. Likewise, the Learning Environment variable, if the learning environment increases by one unit, the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar will increase by -0.349 . Based on the results of hypothesis test 3 which was carried out simultaneously to find out how much the Learning Facilities and Learning Environment variables jointly influence the learning motivation of Class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, the results of the F test calculation were obtained which showed that $F_{count} > F_{table}(5.779 > 1.655)$ and sig value ($0.004 < 0.05$). This shows that the hypothesis which states that there is a positive and significant influence between learning facilities and the learning environment on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar can be accepted. The determination test to see the magnitude of the contribution or contribution of the influence of the independent variable to the dependent variable shows the value of $R^2 = 0.075$. This shows that learning facilities and the learning environment

contribute 7.5 % to student character, while the other 9.2.50 % is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results and discussion in chapter IV, the conclusions that can be put forward in this research are as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Facilities on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) on Learning Facilities (X_1) carried out using SPSS 21.0, namely showing the calculated t value $> t_{table}$ ($3.388 > 1.976$) and a significant value ($0.001 < 0.05$).
2. There is no positive and significant influence between the learning environment on the learning motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) in the learning environment (X_2) carried out using SPSS 21.0, namely showing the calculated t value $< t_{table}$ ($-2.240 < 1.976$) and significant value ($0.027 > 0.05$).
3. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Facilities and the Learning Environment on the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of simultaneous calculations (F test) on Learning Facilities (X_1) and learning environment (X_2) carried out using SPSS 21.0, namely showing the calculated f value $> f_{table}$ ($5.776 > 1.655$) and significant value ($0.004 < 0.05$).

FURTHER STUDY

From the results of research conducted by researchers, there are several suggestions that need to be considered for various parties in order to improve further research as well as the benefits of this research, namely:

1. For Schools
It is hoped that it will help students to utilize more adequate learning facilities when students study at school so that they are more motivated in the learning process.
2. For Students
When the existing learning facilities at school and at home are fulfilled, it is hoped that it will further increase students' learning motivation in order to achieve the desired learning goals.
3. For Further Researchers
Due to the limitations of this research, it is hoped that future research will be more in-depth in exploring information and preparing instruments. So that more facts can be revealed that underlie the influence of learning facilities and the learning environment on student learning motivation.

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